

Emotional Intelligence and Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescent Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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Abstract

The study investigated emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted. Population of the study was 47,297 public senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Sample size of the study was 397 respondents which were determined using Taro Yamene's formula. Stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample size. Two self-structured instruments titled: Emotional Intelligence Scale and Psychological Wellbeing Scale were used for data collection. Face and content validity of the instruments were determined by two experts in Counselling Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Cronbach Alpha method was used to obtain the reliability coefficients of .72 and .71 for Emotional Intelligence Scale and Psychological Wellbeing Scale. Research questions were answered with Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (r), while t-test transformation method was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Results showed that both self-awareness and self-motivation have significant positive relationship and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Recommendation were made that adolescent students should always seek for knowledge that would help to improve their self-awareness of their emotions in order to enhance their psychological wellbeing, and that all adolescent students should embrace the skill of self-motivation as to improve their wellbeing psychologically.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Self-awareness, Self-motivation, Psychological Wellbeing

INTRODUCTION

In the history of human development and growth, the period of adolescence seems to be critical and requires serious attention by parents, teachers and all well-behaved adults in the society in terms of moral and cultural training and behaviour modifications of the adolescents so that they would not constitute nuisance in the society. Adolescence is the period that an individual is neither a child or an adult, hence it the stage in-between children and adulthood that individual will begin to seek for independence, try to belong to different groups, as well as make attempts to know whole lots of things in life. In their table of Noteworthy Markers of Emotional Development in Relation to Social Interaction, Saarni and Camras (2022) sees adolescence as the age period of 13+ years; period of awareness of one's own emotion cycles (e.g., guilt about feeling angry), to facilitates insightful coping, as well as increasing integration of moral character and personal philosophy in dealing with stress and subsequent decisions.

According to Jotika and Anupreet (2017), adolescents are the backbone of any society, and the future of the nation depends on them. However, despite the fact that the future of every nation is highly dependent on the

quality of the adolescents, observations and experience tend to show that the wellbeing of many adolescents in various communities in Rivers State in particular and Nigeria in general is being undermined, which may have contributed to the hike in the rate of deviant behaviours and social vices in the state in recent times. This ugly situation could also have made the study of emotional well-being in young people to be expanded exponentially in recent years (Guerra-Bustamante, León-del-Barco, Yuste-Tosina, López-Ramos & Mendo-Lázaro (2019). However, this present study investigated the relationship between two dimensions of emotional intelligence (self-awareness, self-motivation) and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

The theoretical basis of the study is Rational Emotive Behaviour Theory by Albert Ellis in the 1950s. Rational emotive behaviour therapy (REBT) was introduced by Albert Ellis in 1950s as an approach that can help to identify irrational beliefs and negative thought patterns that may lead to emotional or behavioural issues. Albert Ellis argued that though people exhibit both rational and irrational behaviour, irrational thinking occurs in early illogical learning as a result of continuous

emotional disturbance such as anxiety, depression, hatred, guilt among others. According to the theory, though some illogical thinking in people can attributed to biological limitations, most of them are shaped through socialization processes that are done through parents, teachers, peer groups, mass media and society. The irrational or irrational beliefs of an individual can be explained in four basic principles known as the A-B-C-D principles to enhance proper understanding of the causality between thoughts and emotions. In this regard, Ellis argued by focusing on the philosophic reconstruction of the life style of a person, therapist can devices techniques to make people with maladaptive behaviours to get better and feels better about them. Based on these assumptions, Ellis introduced the reconstruction into the principle to become A-B-C-D-E. A is the Activating Factor, B is the Belief or Self thought, C is the Consequences of self-thought, D is the Disputation and E is the Re-education (E).

Bernard and Dryden (2018) used these principles in his research work on maladaptive behaviour in adolescents and confirmed that it has a significant effect in reshaping the life of adolescents with maladaptive behaviours. In their own experiment, Wood, Barker, Turner and Sheffield (2018) noted that the therapy was able to control the irrational thinking of adolescent students with maladaptive behaviours using the ABC part of the principle. Based on the success of the results, Wood et al. explained that the A which is the Activating Factor is the maladaptive behaviour situation of the person, B which is the Belief refers to the situation where by the adjusted person begins to blame himself with different irrational thinking such as: "I am finished", "everybody is running away from me", "nobody wants to interact with me". But at the C, these irrational thoughts result in isolation, self-denial, hatred for life. The theory is very relevant to this study, since the ABC part of the principle can be used to restructure and control the irrational thinking of adolescent students, and thus make the adolescents to manage their own emotions, as well as others.

Concept of Wellbeing

The concept of wellbeing is seemingly complex in its definition. In fact, there is no one particular definition that is generally accepted in literature. This is because it encompasses a holistic perspective of individual wellness (Schoeman, 2012), which seem to have made the debate over what constitute an individual's

'wellbeing' to take different perspectives in research. For instance, it has been observed that psychology has traditionally focused on unhappiness and paid little attention to positive aspects of human potential (Seligman in Guerra-Bustamante, León-del-Barco, Yuste-Tosina, López-Ramos & Mendo-Lázaro, 2019) and this is evident when studying adolescence (Viejo, Gómez-López & Ortega-Ruiz, 2018). However, Deci and Ryan (2008) noted that majority of researchers employ two common approaches of wellbeing, which according to them are hedonia (subjective wellbeing) and eudaimonia (psychological wellbeing).

Approaches of Wellbeing

1. **Subjective Wellbeing:** This refers to the people's evaluation of their own lives, which includes both cognitive judgements and emotional responses (Tripathi, 2011). The determinants of subjective wellbeing as highlighted by Foxcroft and Roodt (2013) include:
 - a. happiness, which refers to the degree to which a person experiences emotions that are pleasant;
 - b. life satisfaction, which refers to specific areas in a person's life, such as finance, physical health and relationships;
 - c. positive and negative effects, which refer to enjoyment, fun, depression or frustration;
 - d. Socio and economic determinants, which refer to an individual's perceptions on the crime rate, income, unemployment and neighbourhood in which they reside.

2. Psychological Wellbeing

Moe (2012) defined psychological wellbeing as the cornerstone of mental health. Psychological wellbeing encompasses the overall effectiveness of a person's psychological functioning (Nondumiso, 2017). Although, subjective and psychological wellbeing are seen as two different approaches of wellbeing, it is suggested that to obtain optimal wellbeing, there is need to view the two together (Deci & Ryan (2008). Therefore, this study viewed both subjective wellbeing and psychological wellbeing as one, that is, wellbeing. Several factors could determine the wellbeing of an adolescent student. However, this study focused on emotional intelligence as linked to wellbeing of adolescent students.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence can be regarded as a person's ability and capacity to manage and regulate his/ her emotions and that of others, as to make informed or

thoughtful decisions. Robinson, Hull and Petrides (2020) viewed emotional intelligence as the ability to quick and control emotions that make peoples more intelligent. Emotional intelligence is a psychological construct which enables an individual to control his own motions, as well as that of others. Emotion is once state of feeling felt-tendency which could be positive or negative. Emotional intelligence has two types of competencies – personal and social competencies. Personal competencies include major factors namely; self-awareness, self-regulation, self-control, self-motivation, self-consciousness, empathy and social skills. However, there are five dimensions of emotional intelligence. They are self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and relationship management which Goleman cited in Ugoani, Amu .& Kalu (2015) discussed below.

- a. **Self-awareness:** Self-awareness occurs when the individual knows what he is feeling in the moment, and using those preferences to guide decision making, having a realistic assessment of his own abilities and a well-grounded sense of self-confidence.
- b. **Self-regulation:** This involves handling our emotions so that they facilitate rather than interfere with the task at hand; having conscientious and delaying gratification, to pursue goals; recovering well from emotional distress.
- c. **Motivation:** This dimension of emotional intelligence involves using available deepest preferences to move and guide the individual toward desired goals, to help in taking initiative and striving. To improve, and to persevere in the face of setbacks and frustration.
- d. **Empathy:** This is related to sensing what other people are feeling, being able to take their perspective, and cultivating rapport and atonement with a broad diversity of people.
- e. **Relationship management:** Relationship management manifests in handling emotions in relationships well and accurately reading social situations and networks, interacting smoothly; using these skills to persuade and lead, negotiate and settle disputes, for cooperation and teamwork.

Emotional Intelligence and Psychological Well-being

Emotional intelligence is vital in every individual's psychological wellbeing. Ruiz-Aranda, Extremera and Pineda-Galán (2014) who investigated emotional intelligence, life satisfaction and subjective happiness in female student health professionals: the mediating effect of perceived stress in a 12-week follow-up study observed that participants with higher emotional intelligence recorded less perceived stress and higher levels of life satisfaction and happiness, which implies that perceived stress mediates the relationship between emotional intelligence and well-being indicators, such as life satisfaction and happiness. In the same vein, Mehmood and Gulzar (2014) who examined the connection of emotional intelligence with adolescent's psychological well-being (depression and self-esteem) revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between variables of emotional intelligence and self-esteem, and that there is a negative association between emotional intelligence and depression.

Sayeeda and Hameeda (2016) submitted that high emotional intelligence facilitates or push the person toward getting positive sense of self, which contribute to developing high level of self-esteem, and that people who have high level of self-esteem are more open and assertive, and handle hardships more effectively and intelligently, which lead toward excellent performance and leading happy life. Self-awareness develops gradually through a succession of different behaviors all of which relate to the self. Self-motivation is a kind of personal strive that could drive individuals to attain goals within their social environment. When an individual accomplishes a desired goal, it typically results in a sense of positive self-worth, which contributes to personal and professional growth, development and wellbeing. People who are motivated to achieve high would naturally seek out challenging tasks and work hard to succeed, while those who are low in the need for achievement tends to pursue very easy tasks, where the chances of success are high; or they choose tasks that are extremely difficult, where no reasonable person could be expected to succeed.

Statement of the Problem

Emotional intelligence is a psychological construct which enables an individual to manage and control his own motions, as well as that of others and make thoughtful decision that is supposed to affect lives positively. Emotional intelligence is very important in

every individual. However, studies in the past seems to focus much attention on the link between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of adolescents in secondary schools while paying little attention to the psychological wellbeing of those adolescents. However, in recent times, the study of happiness and emotional well-being in young people has expanded exponentially (Guerra-Bustamante, León-del-Barco, Yuste-Tosina, López-Ramos & Mendo-Lázaro, 2019). Nevertheless, available studies to the research show that there is paucity of empirical studies emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing of adolescents in Port Harcourt City of Rivers State, Nigeria, hence the urgent need for this study. This present study therefore, sought to fill the gap in literature by investigating the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. Find out the relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. What is the relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level:

1. There is no significant relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

2. There is no significant relationship between self-motivation and self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the correlational research design. According to Onunkwo as cited in Ogidi (2018), correlational research design is the research design that is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables as well as the direction and magnitude of such relationship. The correlational research design was chosen for the study because it enables the researcher to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

The study was conducted in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State is located in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The climate of Port Harcourt Metropolis is found to be tropical monsoon with lengthy and heavy rainfall between 1,700mm in the North and 4,700mm in the South. Port Harcourt Metropolis has thirty-seven (37) public senior secondary schools (Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2022). There are different industries in The Metropolis is well known for its vast natural resources, with different industries. However, the predominant occupations of the residence of the city is trading and fishing. Port Harcourt city is very unique because it harbors different economic and social activities as well as recreational centres which of course could affect the social activities and behaviour of students in different ways, and this makes this study unique.

Population of the Study

Population of the study is 47,297 students made up of 30,637 students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area and 16,660 students in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area (Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2022).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample of the study is 397 Senior Secondary School two (SSS 2) students in public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis determined using Taro Yamene's sample size formula. The sample size is made up of 257 students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area (112 males, 145 females) and 140 students (72 males, 68 females) in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area. Stratified random sampling

technique was used in selecting the sample of the study. Stratified random sampling technique is a probability sampling method that involves the division of a population into smaller groups called strata (Obilor, 2018). In this study, stratified random sampling technique was used to stratify the population of the study based on gender strata (male and female students) and Local Government Area strata (Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt City) from which 15 schools were selected in Obio/Akpor and 10 schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Areas. Stratified random sampling technique was also used to select 257 students (112 males, 145 females) from the 15 selected schools in Obio/Akpor and 145 students (72 males, 68 females) from the 10 selected schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Areas. However, out of the 397 respondents, only 385 correctly filled and returned the instruments which were used for data analysis.

Research Instruments

Two instruments titled: “Emotional Intelligence Scale” (EIS) and “Psychological Wellbeing Scale” (PWBS) were used for data collection. The Emotional Intelligence Scale was used to elicit information on the students’ emotional intelligence, while the Psychological Wellbeing Scale (PWBS) was used to collect information on the students’ psychological wellbeing. Each of the scales contained 5 items; hence the instrument was made up of 10 items in all prepared on a four-point response scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) with weighted 4 points to Strongly Disagree (SD) with weighted 1 point respectively.

Validity of the Instrument

The face and content validity of the instrument-Students’ Emotional Intelligence and Psychological Wellbeing Questionnaire” (SEIPWBQ) was determined by two experts in Counselling Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The experts reviewed the items of the two instruments in terms of their clarity, suitability of the words, content coverage,

adequacy and relevance of the items in addressing the purpose of the study and research questions, and made corrections which formed the basis for the final print out of the instruments.

Reliability of the Instruments

To determine the reliability of the instrument, 20 copies of the instrument were administered to 20 SSS 2 students in one public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Local Government Area that are not selected for the study which the researcher retrieved on the spot. The Cronbach Alpha method was used to calculate the reliability coefficients for the instrument with the aid of the SPSS software version 25 which yielded 0.72 and 0.71 reliability coefficients for Emotional Intelligence Scale and Psychological Wellbeing Scale respectively.

Methods of Data Analysis

The Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation (r) was used to answer the research questions, while t-test transformation method was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The t-test transformation method was used to compute the significance of the Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation (r) using the formula below:

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{N - 2}{1 - r^2}}$$

Where, t = t-test transformation, r = correlation coefficient value, N = total number of cases (population) at $df = N - 2$.

T-transformation or t-distribution method is appropriate for testing the significance of the computed correlation coefficient in the absence of SPSS irrespective of the sample size of the study since it approximates the z-transformation as the data tends to infinity (Wonu, Victor-Edema & Ndimele, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data collected for this study were analyzed and presented using tables.

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 1: PPMC for Self-awareness and Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescent Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis (n = 385)

Variables	N	x	SD	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r	Remark
				$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$			
Self-awareness	385	3.09	0.55	1182	3774	3761	0.130	Positive
Psychological Wellbeing	385	3.17	0.39	1212	3904			

Source: Field Data, 2022.

From results in Table 1, it can be observed that r-value of 0.130 is positive which shows that there is a positive relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The low r-value indicates that high self-awareness can only result to a little improvement in the

psychological wellbeing of the adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 2: PPMC for Self-motivation and Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescent Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis (n = 385)

Variables	N	x	SD	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r	Remark
				$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$			
Self-motivation	385	3.02	0.62	1152	3622	3668	0.139	Positive
Psychological Wellbeing	385	3.17	0.39	2121	3904			

Source: Field Data, 2022.

Results in Table 2 shows that there is a positive relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis with r-value = 0.139.

adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis because all adolescent students do not display self-motivation skill at the same time.

Test of Hypotheses

However, the low correlation (r) value 0.139 indicates that self-motivation does not strongly determinant psychological wellbeing of adolescent students. The low positive r-value shows that self-motivation alone does not strongly determine psychological wellbeing of

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H01: There is no significant relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 3: T-test Transformation of Relationship between Self-awareness and Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescent Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Variables	N	x	SD	df	r	t-trans	t-crit	α	Remark
Self-awareness	385	3.09	0.55						
				383	0.130	2.556	1.96	0.05	S
Psychological Wellbeing	385	3.17	0.39						

S = Significant at 0.05 Significance Level

Results in Table 3 shows that at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom (df) of 383, $r = 0.130$, t-transformation ($t\text{-trans}$) = 2.556 and t-critical ($t\text{-crit}$) = 1.96. Since $t\text{-trans}$ value of 2.556 > $t\text{-crit}$ value of 1.96 at 0.05 significance level and degree of freedom (df) of 383, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis” was therefore rejected. This

implies that self-awareness is significantly related to psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

H02: There is no significant relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 4: T-test Transformation of Relationship between Self-motivation and Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescent Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Variables	N	x	SD	df	r	t-trans	t-crit	α	Remark
Self-motivation	385	3.02	0.62						
				383	0.139	2.736	1.96	0.05	S
Psychological Wellbeing	385	3.17	0.39						

S = Significant at 0.05 Significance Level

From the data in Table 4, it can be observed that at 0.05 level of significance and df of 383, $r = 0.139$, t-transformation ($t\text{-trans}$) = 2.736 and t-critical ($t\text{-crit}$) = 1.96. Since $t\text{-trans}$ (2.736) > $t\text{-crit}$ value (1.96) at 0.05 and df of 386, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis” was not accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Self-awareness and Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescent Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Results for research question one and hypothesis one showed that there is a positive relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of

adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis, and that the relationship between self-awareness and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis is significantly related. The low r-value implies that high self-awareness can result to a little improvement in the psychological wellbeing of the adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This result is because self-awareness does not occur suddenly on its own through one particular behaviour; rather it develops gradually through a succession of different behaviors all of which relate to the self. To corroborate the finding of this study, Sayeeda and Hameeda (2016) submitted that high emotional intelligence facilitates or push the person toward getting positive sense of self, which contribute to developing high level of self-esteem, and that people who have high level of self-esteem are more open and assertive,

and handle hardships more effectively and intelligently, which lead toward excellent performance and leading happy life.

Self-motivation and Psychological Wellbeing of Adolescent Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Data analysis for research question two and hypothesis two indicated that there is a positive relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis, and that the relationship between self-motivation and psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis is significantly related. The low positive r-value shows that self-motivation alone does not strongly determine psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis because all adolescent students do not display self-motivation skill at the same time. This finding corroborates Seligman (2019) when he asserted that self-motivation serves as personal strive which drives individuals to attain goals within their social environment. When an individual accomplishes a desired goal, it typically results in a sense of positive self-worth, which contributes to personal and professional growth, development and wellbeing.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated emotional intelligence and psychological wellbeing of adolescent Student's in Port Harcourt Metropolis. From the results of the study, it can be observed that the two dimensions of emotional intelligent considered in the study such as self-awareness and self-motivation have significant and positive relationship with the psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. It was therefore concluded that emotional intelligence is a factor that determine psychological wellbeing of adolescent students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Thus, the higher the emotional intelligence, the better the psychological wellbeing of the adolescent student's in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

IMPLICATIONS FOR COUNSELLING

The following are some of the counselling implications of the study:

1. There is need for all secondary schools in Rivers State have well equipped counselling units where adolescent students can be provided with up-to-date information about how to improve in their emotional intelligence.

2. Counsellors could also team up to develop a model for measuring psychological wellbeing of students within Rivers State or Nigerian context.

REMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Adolescent students should always seek for knowledge that would help to improve their self-awareness of their emotions in order to enhance their psychological wellbeing.
2. All adolescent students should embrace the skill of self-motivation as to improve their wellbeing psychologically.

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